

mfs2023
INL | Braga, Portugal

Certificate of Speaker Participation

The MFS2023 Organizing Committee certifies that

Ane Laura Sousa

participated as a **speaker with the oral presentation: "Influenza A virus liquid condensates – An ultrastructural study"** in the **MFS2023**, held at Braga, Portugal, at the INL- International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory from 27th to 29th, September 2023.

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